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Information and communication technologies in the foreign policy strategy of modern states*Babina V. O., Ph. D. of Political Sciences,**Associate Professor at the Department of International Relations and Law**Odessa Polytechnic State University**Myrhorodska O. O., Third-year student at the Department of International Relations and Law, Odessa Polytechnic State University*

Until recently, the public diplomacy of any state relied on the traditional media management system mainly. However, the modern technological breakthrough, characterized by the widespread introduction of the latest means of communication and communication into all spheres of public life, has also contributed to large-scale changes in the forms and methods of foreign policy activities.

Achievements in the field of information and communication technologies are used by political actors to analyze the economic, social, and political situation in individual countries and regions, as well as to prepare public opinion for making important government decisions. On the Internet (primarily in social networks), new methods of information and psychological impact on the mass consciousness are regularly tested.

Information and communication processes that arise in international relations affect not only the foreign policy situation but also the situation within states. These processes, if properly organized, contribute to the formation in the minds of the people of a positive image of state power, its institutions and leaders, which in general contributes both to the development of the mass political consciousness of the population and to an increase in the potential of the state's foreign policy, and this is of no small importance, especially if we take into account that that in the modern world there are no clear boundaries between domestic and foreign policy, and foreign policy activity is increasingly closely intertwined with the solution of internal national problems [2, 178].

The determining factor in the development of communication processes in the modern world is informatization and modern information technologies, which cover the most diverse areas of social, spiritual and material life of a person. They turn into a resource that easily overcomes any obstacles and influences world events and international relations.

In scientific studies that touch upon the problems of using information and communication technologies in foreign policy communication, a wide variety of tools of information influence and control over the information sphere are considered - propaganda, licensing, social advertising, distribution of wave frequencies, censorship, public discussions, etc.

The peculiar digitalization of geopolitics significantly increases the importance of public diplomacy, which, when working with local and foreign audiences, allows you to effectively, outside of time and space, broadcast the

official position of the state and form public opinion on socially significant issues [1, 432]. Dynamically mimicking technologies cause more and more active use in politics of modern instruments of influence of social networks, forums, Internet portals, etc.

A significant factor in the effective operation of state structures in the information and communication space is the speed of response to processes and events, and not to the detriment of the possibility of intelligibly explaining the country's official position. The latter is extremely important in high-profile cases, as it contributes to a convincing refutation of the so-called fake news.

At the same time, the preventive creation of a narrative that meets the national interests of the state can significantly minimize the negative consequences of the activities of external forces in the information and communication space, as a rule, seeking to fill its voids [3, 251].

Digital diplomacy in political relations is favored by timeless access to the global network, the possibility of creating appropriate technological platforms in the information and communication space, wide audience coverage, etc. politics in general. The implementation by official structures of direct contacts with a foreign audience is changing its form and content.

The risks in the field of ensuring national security are also intensifying due to the fact that at the present stage, in addition to states, an increasing number of participants, both legitimate and illegitimate, are included in world politics.

Each such political actor has its own interests and goals, often intertwined with the interests of other participants in global communication interactions, as well as resources, the volume of which can correspond to the state budgets of individual countries and even exceed them.

Experts believe that in the conditions of the accelerated development of the digital environment, diverse political actors will increasingly resort to the advantages of information and communication technologies, including to achieve military-political goals.

Thus, in the conditions of a rapidly mimicking digital reality, the development and preventive application of innovations in the information and communication sphere in political practice will, apparently, greatly contribute to ensuring state interests in certain areas. This is already evidenced by the first successes of some countries.

References:

1. Martin-Shields C. P., Bodanac N. Peacekeeping's digital economy: the role of communication technologies in post-conflict economic growth //International Peacekeeping. – 2018. – Т. 25. – №. 3. – pp. 420-445.
2. Roztocki N., Soja P., Weistroffer H. R. The role of information and communication technologies in socioeconomic development: towards a multi-dimensional framework //Information Technology for Development. – 2019. – Т. 25. – №. 2. – pp. 171-183.
3. Гарматій О. В. Інформаційне забезпечення міжнародної діяльності: роль і значення інформаційних агентств //Міжнародні відносини: теоретико-практичні аспекти. – 2018. – №. 1. – pp. 244-254.